

Review Article

A Review of Herbal Treatment for Peptic Ulcer

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ABSTRACT

Peptic ulcer is caused by mucosal injury that penetrates through muscularis mucosal covering and forms a wound which is surrounded by acute and chronic inflammation. Peptic ulcer comprised of both duodenal and stomach ulcers. Peptic ulcer disease is an imbalance of protective mucosal blockage and aggressive gastric luminal factors like lipid peroxidation, nitric oxide and acid pepsin secretion. Standard treatments of peptic ulcers using H₂ (Histamine Receptor) antagonists and H⁺ pump inhibitors have shown drug interactions, mild to severe adverse effects, and also relapses in some cases. While the medicinal plants and their antiulcer phytoconstituent's are advantageous in treatment of peptic ulcer. There are so many plants which constitute have numerous floral products that have been turned up to possess antiulcer activity. Phytoconstituents like flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, kaempferol etc. are useful in treating peptic ulcers. This review focusses on medicinal plants whose phytoconstituents have a gastroprotective role and thus they can be used for prevention or treatment of peptic ulcer.

Keywords: antiulcer phytogetic compounds, proton pump inhibitor, botanical products, peptic ulcer

Introduction

Peptic ulcers are acid prompt lesions specified by discontinuation in the inner lining of the gastrointestinal tract with the defect expanding into the submucosa or muscularis propria.¹ Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is specified by divested mucosa in the inner lining of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, stomach and duodenal walls because of pepsin and gastric acid secretion. It penetrates into the muscularis propria layer of the gastric epithelium. It frequently occurs in the proximal duodenum and stomach. Peptic ulcer disease has many reasons; but greater number of disease etiology is due to Helicobacter pylori-associated peptic ulcer disease

and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs-associated peptic ulcer disease.² Peptic ulcers comprise both duodenal and gastric ulcers.³ Standard treatments of peptic ulcers using H₂ (Histamine Receptor) antagonists and H⁺ pump inhibitors have shown drug interactions, mild to severe adverse effects, and also relapses in some cases. While the medicinal plants and their antiulcer phytoconstituent's are advantageous in treatment of peptic ulcer. There are so many plants which constitute have numerous floral products that have been turned up to possess antiulcer activity. Phytoconstituents like flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, kaempferol etc. are useful in treating

peptic ulcers.⁴ This review focusses on medicinal plants whose phytoconstituents have a gastroprotective role and thus they can be used for prevention or treatment of peptic ulcer. Plants are gaining more authenticity in present era because they lack significant side effects and are safe.⁵ There are so many spices as well as herbs have been studied by various investigators for their antiulcer effects to gain a favorable result. Gastroprotective activities of a large number of medicinal plants and dietary nutrients have shown to possess fewer side effects.⁶ Severe toxicity and antiulcer activity of some medicinal plants has been studied by us in this article. Our research aimed that these reviewed medicinal plants could avert ulcer in a dose-dependent manner. From histological studies it

comes out that these medicinal plants did not have any severe toxicity. Initial photochemical screening of these medicinal plants spots the presence of significant secondary metabolites like tannins and flavonoids.

A variety of floral products have been revealed to have antiulcer activity. Active postulates of antiulcer activity are Flavonoids, tannins, lupeol, nimbin, quercetin and papain, terpenoids.

1. *Ficus Microcarpa*

28 crystalline components have been isolated from the stem of *Ficus microcarpa*.

Table 1: *Ficus Microcarpa*^{7,8,9}

Local name	Chinese banyan, Indian Laurel
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Raosales
Family	Moraceae
Genus	Ficus
Species	F. microcarpa
Antiulcer constituents	Lupeol

Spectral data and literature have been used to determine their structure. These compounds comprise 14 triterpenoids, 1 fatty alcohol, 8

steroids, 1 coumarin, 1 flavane, two 4-hydroxybenzoates, and 1 carotenoid-like compound.¹⁰

2. *Azadirachta indica*

Table 2: *Azadirachta indica*^{11,12,13}

Local name	Neem, Indian Lilac, doyaro
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Sapindales
Family	Meliaceae
Genus	Azadirachta
Species	A.indica
Antiulcer constituents	Flavonoids , tannins, nimbin

Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) is of the best commercially exploitable standard medicinal plant used in India. During the last 50 years, not only the chemistry of the neem compounds has been studied until now but also a huge progress has

been made in regard to the medicinal petitions of neem. It is thought as a useful source of distinctive natural products for origination of medicines in anticipation of various diseases and also for the establishment of industrial products.¹⁴

3. *Alstonia scholaris*

Table 3. *Alstonia scholaris*^{15,16,17}

Local name	Blackboard tree, devil's tree
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Gentianales
Family	Apocynaceae
Genus	<i>Alstonia</i>
Species	<i>A.scholaris</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Triterpenoids, lupeol

Alstonia scholaris is most frequently found in Southeast Asia. In standard medicine

pharmacological activities are ascribed to the leaves and stem of this plant.¹⁸

4. *Bauhinia variegata*

Table 4. *Bauhinia variegata*^{19,20,21}

Local name	Orchid tree, mountain ebony
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	<i>Bauhinia</i>
Species	<i>B.variegata</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Chrysin a flavonoid

Jatropha variegata is conventionally used in Yemeni folk medicine for bactericidal and hemostatic motives.²²

5. *Butea frondosa*

Table 5. *Butea frondosa*^{23,24,25}

Local name	Palas, flame of forest
Kingdom	plantae
Class	Angiosperms

Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	Butea
Species	B. frondosa
Antiulcer constituents	BF-1(quercetin) a flavonoid, pranthrocyanidin

The flavonoid with drawn fraction from the ethyl acetate fraction (BF-1) of *Butea frondosa* stem shown different germicidal activity when it was

trialed against one hundred twenty-nine bacterial strains belonging to nine different genera of both gram +ve and gram -ve types.²⁶

6. *Carica papaya*

Table 6. *Carica papaya*^{27,28,29}

Local name	Papaw, pawpaw
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Brassicales
Family	Caricaceae
Genus	<i>Carica</i>
Species	<i>C. papaya</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Kaempherol, quercetin, papain, chymopapain

Papaya belongs to the family Caricaceae and is renowned for its nutritional and therapeutic properties. Since ancient era different extracts

from papaya plant have been used for the medicinal aims.³⁰

7. *Senna alexandrina*

Table 7. *Senna alexandrina*^{31,32,33}

Local name	Sana makki
Kingdom	Plantea
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	<i>Senna</i>
Species	<i>S. alexandrina</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Quercimeritin, kempferol

Senna comprise of the dried leaves and fruits of *Cassia senna*. The *senna* plants are small shrubs of

Leguminosae cultured either in Somalia, the Arabian Peninsula and near the Nile River.

Tinnevelly senna is obtained from cultured plants mainly in South India and Pakistan. Damaged

leaves and lower quality products are often used for making galenicals.³⁴

8. *Nigella sativa*

Table 8. *Nigella sativa*^{35,36,37}

Local name	Black cumin, nigella or kalonji
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Ranunculales
Family	Ranunculaceae
Genus	<i>Nigella</i>
Species	<i>N. sativa</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Kempferol, thymoquinone

Nigella sativa is a broadly used medicinal plant all over the world. It is most common in many conventional therapeutics like Tibb, Siddha, Ayurveda and Unani. In past seeds and oil have folklore usage in numerous systems of food and medicines. The seeds of *N. sativa* have been broadly used in the cure of numerous diseases and ailments. In Islamic literature, it is believed as one of the significant varieties of medicine. It has been suggested for using on ordinary basis in Tibb-e-Nabawi. It has broadly widely used as liver

diuretics, digestive, appetite stimulant, analgesics, anti-bacterial and in skin disorders, anti-diarrheal, appetite stimulant and liver tonics. Extensive studies on *N. sativa* have been studied by various investigators and a broad spectrum of its pharmacological actions have been surveyed which may comprise antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, bronchodilator antidiabetic, anticancer, immunomodulator, analgesic, spasmolytic, hepatoprotective, renal protective and gastro-protective antioxidant properties, etc.³⁸

9. *Trigonella foenum-graceum*

Table 9. *Trigonella foenum-graceum*^{39,40,41}

Local name	Methi, fenugreek
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Genus	<i>Trigonella</i>
Species	<i>T. foenum-graceum</i>
Antiulcer constituents	Flavonoides, terpenes, kempferol

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* Linn.), momentary annual medicinal plant belongs to Fabaceae family, is used on a large scale in so many parts of the world as herb, traditional medicine, food and spice. Fenugreek is ancient medicinal plants

and Ayurveda and Chinese medicine have been cited its health promoting effects. The examination into the pharmacological actions and chemical composition have witnessed a revival in current years.⁴²

10. *Ficus religiosa*

Table 10. *Ficus religiosa*^{43,44,45}

Local name	Bo tree, bodhi tree, peepul and sacred fig
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperms
Order	Rosales
Family	Moraceae
Genus	Ficus
Species	F. religiosa
Antiulcer constituents	Kempferol, tannis, terpenoides, flavonoides, quercetin

Religiosa came out as a good source of conventional medicine for the treatment of asthma, diabetes, gastric problems, inflammatory disorders, infectious disorders, sexual disorders, diarrhea and epilepsy.⁴⁶

11. *Artemisia douglasiana*

Table 11. *Artemisia douglasiana*^{47,48,49}

Local name	Matico, dream plant
Kingdom	Plantae
Class	Angiosperm
Order	Asterales
Family	Asteraceae
Genus	Artemisia
Species	A. douglasiana
Antiulcer constituents	Terpinen, terpenoids, flavonoids

In eradication of metronidazole and clarithromycin-resistant strain the use of *Artemisia douglasiana* is a useful alternative treatment.⁵⁰

Conclusion

From this review, we conclude that peptic ulcer may be treated through extracts of medicinal plants. There are many traditional medicinal plants such as *Carica papaya*, *Ficus religiosa* and *Butea frondosa* etc. which possess antiulcer activity containing phytochemical compounds. Synthetic medicine of peptic ulcer has shown adverse side effects and

various drug interaction. On the other hand, herbal drugs are more reliable and have fewer toxic effects even in high concentration. Because medicinal plants do not have adverse side effects that's why they are commonly used in present era. Phytochemical compounds such as flavonoid's, terpenoids, tannins, and nimbin etc. have significant anti-ulcer activity. Our investigation of various medicinal plants showed that they possess anti-ulcer activity.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of Interest.

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Contributions of the Authors

ZUN,UZ,WN devised the plan
ZUN,UZ,WN wrote the manuscript

